

XXI ICICU

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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The Book of abstracts contains the materials of invited, plenary and poster presentations reports on XXI International Conference on Inorganic Chemistry Ukraine (XXI ICICU) which take place in Uzhhorod June 3-6, 2024. At the conference were considered issues of solid state chemistry, solid inorganic materials, crystal chemistry, synthesis of new compounds for modern medicine and pharmaceutical chemistry, chemistry and physics of materials, atomic and electronic structure of solid inorganic materials, materials for "green" chemistry. The conference will cover issues on solid state chemistry, solid-state inorganic materials, crystal chemistry, synthesis of new compounds for modern medicine and pharmaceutical chemistry, materials chemistry and physics, atomic and electronic structure of solid inorganic materials, materials for "green" chemistry, etc. The reports contain the latest scientific results and advanced research methods in the field: 1. Chemistry of inorganic and coordination compounds, including medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry; 2. Characterization and properties of new inorganic substances, crystal chemistry; 3. Physical inorganic chemistry, nanochemistry; 4. Dual-use materials, alternative energy sources, environmental chemistry.

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TAILORED MICROWAVE DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES IN PEROVSKITE CERAMICS $1-x\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3-x[\text{Ca},\text{Sr},\text{La}]\text{TiO}_3$

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Current microwave (MW) communication systems utilize high-quality thermostable dielectrics with a specific range of permittivity (ϵ) for optimal performance. Operating in the millimeter wave range, 5G requires materials with significantly lower ϵ compared to its predecessors. While alternative approaches like "whispering gallery" oscillations have been explored, they remain technically complex and impractical for widespread implementation. Therefore, 5G development requires new MW materials with tunable dielectric properties and minimal losses for efficient signal transmission. Finding the optimal material involves trade-offs. Materials based solely on electronic strain provide low ϵ and minimal losses but exhibit a negative temperature coefficient of permittivity ($\text{TC}\epsilon$) or positive temperature coefficient of resonance frequency (τ_f). On the other hand, materials with a dominant ionic strain mechanism provide higher ϵ , but at the cost of opposite sign of τ_f and higher losses. Composites combining materials with negative and positive τ_f can offer high thermal stability.

This work investigates the preparation of perovskite-based microwave dielectric ceramics with tailored compositions $(1-x\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3-x[\text{Ca},\text{Sr},\text{La}]\text{TiO}_3$, where Ln is La, Nd, Sm) for optimal microwave dielectric properties including near-zero temperature coefficient of resonant frequency (τ_f).

Ceramic samples were prepared by the solid-state reactions technique. Highly pure Ln_2O_3 (Ln = La, Nd, Sm), MgO, MCO_3 (M is Ca, Sr), and TiO_2 (99.9%) were weighted according to the required stoichiometry and mixed with ethanol for 4 hours. The mixed powders were calcined at 1250 °C for 3 h. After checking for phase purity using powder x-ray diffraction, the powders were pressed at 100 MPa. The pellets were sintered at 1650 °C for 2 h in air.

The single-phase solid solutions $1-x\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3-x[\text{Ca},\text{Sr},\text{La}]\text{TiO}_3$ were obtained in the whole range of compositions (x). The bulk density, microstructure, and microwave dielectric properties of the samples were investigated depending on the x value and sintering temperature. Higher sintering temperatures are found to effectively promote densification and improve the dielectric properties of the ceramic samples.

The quality factors $Q \times f$ of $\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3$, (Ln is La, Nd, Sm), $\text{Ca}_{0.61}\text{La}_{0.26}\text{TiO}_3$ and $\text{Ca}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{TiO}_3$ was 50 000, 65 000, 53 000, 11 000 and 7 500 GHz, respectively. By adjusting the ratio of the end-members in the solid solution ($\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Ca}_{0.61}\text{La}_{0.26}\text{TiO}_3$ or $\text{Ca}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{TiO}_3$), the temperature coefficient of resonant frequency (τ_f) can be reduced towards zero. With the decrease in the content of $\text{Ln}(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5})\text{O}_3$ (decrease in x from 1 to 0) the temperature coefficient of resonant frequency τ_f increases from -55 to 300 ppm/K. The optimal microwave dielectric properties with a dielectric constant ϵ of 25, $Q \times f$ of 21 400 GHz (at 8.0 GHz), and τ_f near zero were obtained for $0.6\text{NdMg}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}\text{O}_3-0.4\text{Ca}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{TiO}_3$ sintered at 1550 °C for 3 h. The higher density and well-developed grain growth of this sample was observed. The dielectric resonator is a good candidate for high Q-factor applications such as narrowband microwave filters with high selectivity, for oscillators with precise frequency control and in dielectric resonator antennas with good radiation efficiency and high directivity.

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